

New European Bauhaus Academy

The future of the NEB Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

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European Commission
JRC

**Circular
Bio-based
Europe**

Joint Undertaking

Co-funded by
the European Union

The NEB: from vision to implementation

The NEB Academy: Skills, Knowledge, Innovation and Business Development

27 February 2026

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What has the NEB achieved since 2020?

- ✓ **NEB Community** across Europe
- ✓ **Bottom-up initiatives and funding projects**
- ✓ **NEB objectives in EU programmes and policies**, and within the European Commission
- ✓ **Tools guidelines** to support NEB projects (i.e. NEB Compass, Investment guidelines)
- ✓ **Awareness, mobilisation, sharing of best practices**

2,000

Members of the
NEB Community

700

projects

9

EU programmes
supporting NEB

EUR **1.4** billion

Under 2021-2027
MFF

NEB in current EU political priorities

NEB in current political priorities: affordable housing

*“A home is not just four walls and a roof.
It is safety, warmth, a place for family and friends.*

*This is more than a housing crisis.
It is a social crisis.
It tears at Europe's social fabric.*

*Still this year we will present the first ever
European Affordable Housing Plan.
To make housing more affordable,
more sustainable, and of better quality.
It will be a European effort, anchored
in local realities.”*

Affordable Housing Package – 16 December 2025

- ❖ European Affordable Housing Plan
- ❖ European Housing Construction Strategy
- ❖ Revised EU State aid rules
- ❖ **Commission Communication on the New European Bauhaus: from vision to implementation, and proposal for Council Recommendation**

NEB Communication

Sets EU vision & priorities

Launches tools & initiatives

Mobilises EU funding & markets

Commission-led

NEB Recommendation

Invites MS to act

Embed NEB in national/regional frameworks

Strengthens multilevel governance

Member State-owned

Key message

Scale up the NEB and move from inspiration & experimentation to systemic change

New European Bauhaus

Three objectives of the Communication

Enhancing **circularity, sustainability** and **innovation in the built environment** by supporting the circular economy and bioeconomy, promoting research, scaling up innovative solutions and reinforcing community resilience to natural disasters.

Empowering citizens through **participatory processes** to strengthen **democratic, inclusive** and **resilient** neighbourhoods.

Harnessing the transformative **power of education, arts** and **culture** to boost creativity and innovation for local transformation.

4 enablers

**NEB COMMUNITY
AND GRASSROOTS
PARTICIPATION**

**THE NEB ACADEMY:
KNOWLEDGE,
SKILLS AND
BUSINESS
DEVELOPMENT**

**FUNDING AND
GOVERNANCE**

**INTERNATIONAL
DIMENSION**

What is the NEB Academy?

- **Launched by the Commission in 2022 to accelerate the up-skilling and re-skilling of workers in the construction ecosystem**
- Will now **become the core infrastructure of the NEB** for knowledge and research, safe experimentation and innovation, and skills development
- Focus on the **built environment**
- **Building on work initiated by universities and competence centres** to foster research, pioneer new models of education and trainings and connect knowledge with business applications
- Provide a dynamic and evidence-based link between the NEB Facility's **R&I and Roll-Out components**

What are the building blocks of the NEB Academy?

Stream 1

Knowledge
& Research

Leverage digital tools to **structure, store, share, and assess knowledge and data. Better connect** ongoing research activities, increasing their potential impact in terms of **applied research, tested solutions, and replicable models**

Target audience: NEB Community members, practitioners, professionals, researchers, businesses, and public authorities

Key actions:

- **NEB as a space for frontier research** (i.e. scientific publications and academic gatherings)
- **NEB Knowledge Hub for Result and Impact** will make learnings and best practices from NEB projects available and accessible
- **NEB indicators and guidance tools** to assess impact of NEB initiatives/projects
- **Catalogue of NEB good practices and blueprints on affordable and resilient housing** will highlight state-of-the-art solutions

Stream 2

Translate research insights into practical skills, develop innovative training frameworks and learning pathways and strengthen the pedagogical quality, coherence and certification of existing NEB-related training across Europe

Target audience: national training institutions, workers across value-chains, students, project developers, public authorities

Key actions:

- upskilling and **reskilling of the workforce in the construction ecosystem**, in particular for bio- and nature-based construction
- **university-business partnerships** to develop skills and competences in NEB-related sectors (e.g. workforce and future entrepreneurs)

Stream 3

Enable **experimentation environments** and provide **advisory services** and **toolboxes** to trial NEB blueprints. Create pathways for community-led and interdisciplinary innovation to **grow, replicate, and reach the market**

Target audience: SMEs, start-ups and businesses moving to new sustainable practices, emerging projects from the NEB Facility R&I, local practitioners

Key actions:

- **Innovation pilots and pre-acceleration pathways** for early-stage innovators to accompany start-ups and scale-up of innovative, sustainable practices
- **NEB Advisory Hub** to improve access to funding for smaller players and facilitate private, public, and blended finance
- **NEB Labs:** testing and experimentations of solutions developed by the NEB Community

NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS PRIZES

NEB BOOST FOR SMALL MUNICIPALITIES

beautiful | sustainable | together

Discover

2026 novelties
and apply with
your project or idea
by **17 March 2026**

**THE
FESTIVAL** of the
NEW EUROPEAN
BAUHAUS
Life. Spaces. Buildings.

COME AND JOIN
THE MAKERS OF CHANGE

BRUSSELS
9-13 JUNE
2026